

generally does not kill fungi present inside glumes. Although treating seeds with hot water is effective against internal pathogens, the process is precise and difficult for farmers to adopt. Infected seeds weigh less than healthy and fully filled grains; so mechanical separation based on specific gravity would help differentiate healthy and diseased seeds.

In a field experiment during the punja season (Oct-Jan) at the Moncompu RRS, seeds of Bharathy (highly susceptible to sheath rot) were treated with different concentrations of common salt. Seeds that sank to the bottom in each solution were washed in three changes of clean water and broadcast.

Both sheath blight and sheath rot were reduced as salt concentration increased (see table). In general, sheath blight incidence was low but sheath rot disease was moderate up to 7.5% concentration of the salt solution. Reduction in sheath rot at a

Intensity of sheath blight and sheath rot diseases in seeds treated with different concentrations of salt solution. Kerala, India.

Concn (%) of salt solution	Sheath blight score ^a	Sheath rot score ^b
0.0 (untreated control)	1.8	3.6
2.5	1.5	3.6
5.0	0.6	3.1
1.5	0.4	3.1
10.0	0.2	2.6
12.5	0.1	1.4
15.0	0.3	0.9
17.5	0.2	0.3
20.0	0.2	0.1
C.D.	0.8	1.0

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES) scale: 1 = lesions limited to lower 1/4 of leaf sheaths, 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves. ^b1976 SES scale: 1 = less than 1% [of tillers affected] (= to resistant check), 9 = 50-100% (= to susceptible check).

concentration of 15% was significant compared to that at lower concentrations.

Mechanical separation of seeds by the method used in this experiment is cheap and simple, and can easily be used by farmers. ■

Transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka and Yokogi by seed

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The transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, the pathogen for rice leaf scald, was investigated in three separate trials. In the first, the fungus was detected by the standard blotter method in seeds of Cheena I collected from a heavily infected farmer's field. The seeds were examined periodically for the presence of the fungus. In the second test, surface-sterilized seeds of Cheena I were rolled in actively sporulating culture of the fungus and were sown in sterilized potted field soils. In another test, seeds from severely infected plants of Cheena I and IET2914 were similarly sown in sterilized field soil. Observations on the appearance of the disease on the seedlings raised in the two tests were recorded until the plants reached maturity.

Isolation of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* from rice seeds of cultivar Cheena I. West Bengal, India.

Date of observation ^a	Seeds(%) giving the fungus	
	Unsterilized	Sterilized
1 Aug 1977	1.14	0
20 Aug	1.13	0
1 Sep	0.86	0
1 Oct	0.61	0
1 Nov	0.00	0
18 Nov	0.00	0

^aSeeds were collected on 26 July 1977.

With the blotter method, the leaf scald fungus could be detected from seed samples of cultivar Cheena I within the first 3 months of collection (see table). The percentage of fungal isolations gradually declined with time of storage. Low percentages of seeds (0.61-1.14%) yielded the fungus. Success in isolating the fungus from unsterilized seed samples and failure to do so from surface-sterilized seeds indicated that the pathogen was externally seedborne.

The plants raised from seeds artificially inoculated with the fungus and from seeds harvested from scald-infected, plants of both Cheena I and IET2914 remained disease free until maturity.

Although a low percentage of rice seeds may have borne the leaf scald fungus *R. oryzae*, the exact role of this seedborne infection in causing the disease could not be established. ■

Studies on sheath rot of rice

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Sheath rot of rice caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gams and Hawkeworth has recently become serious in northern India.

A partially selective medium for the fungus has been developed by incorporating 100 ppm Dithane 2-78 and 750 ppm Dicrystin S in Kirchoffs medium. The infected leaf sheaths and grains from diseased panicles were stored at room temperature (8-40° C) and under field conditions to study the survival of the pathogen. The fungus was isolated periodically from diseased parts on Kirchoffs medium. The fungus survived as long as 4 months in seed and 7 months in leaf sheath kept at room conditions and as long as 10 months in leaf sheaths in the field.

The disease development and the meteorological factors for the corresponding period were compared for 3 consecutive seasons from 1976-78 kharif to determine the most favorable conditions. Disease development was maximum when the minimum temperature was 17-20° C and the minimum relative humidity, 40-50% at flowering. The maximum temperature, maximum relative humidity, rainfall, and sunshine could not be correlated with disease severity.

Of the inoculation methods tried, injection of the spore suspension and placement of the pathogen grown on pearl millet inside the boot leaf sheath 7-4 days before flowering gave maximum disease in the field.

Five varieties — Basmati 370, Chinsurah Boro II, Hom Thong, Sigadis,

and TKM6 — were resistant to the disease under artificial inoculation.

Chemical control trials for 2 consecutive seasons showed that 3 sprays of carbenazim (0.05%), benomyl (0.05%), and Brestanol (0.1%) gave good disease control in the field. ■

Epidemiological adaptation by the rice blast pathogen during adverse weather

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During kharif 1979, dark-brown to blackish lesions were observed on the panicle-bearing and ensheathed lower internodes and nodes of the stems in plants of a susceptible local rice cultivar Tulsiphool at the Faizabad RRS. The lesions were either eye-shaped or irregular; the latter were more common on the panicle axis and below its base. Blurred brown blotches appeared on the sheath encasing the affected part of the stem. There was mycelial growth with abundant sporulation on the ensheathed lesions on nodes and internodes (see photo). The naked lesions rarely sporulated. In advanced stages the lesions on the sheath also sporulated underneath.

Ensheathed lesions on nodes and internodes, and blotches on the sheath encasing the affected part of the stem of the cultivar Tulsiphool. Faizabad, U.P., India.

No breaking at the panicle base was seen.

Long sheaths encasing the nodes and internodes are a peculiar characteristic of Tulsiphool and appear to provide favorable conditions for the development of those symptoms. The disease appeared during the last 2 weeks of October when night temperatures were relatively mild and considerable dew collected on the leaves. The microclimate was therefore suitable for disease development in the ensheathed nodes and

internodes. The general weather during the growing season, however, was unusually dry and not favorable for blast development (see table).

The occurrence of the disease on highly susceptible cultivars such as Tulsiphool under adverse situations appears epidemiologically significant. However, the disease may only be regarded as a "sleeper disease" in Eastern U. P. because of the requirement of critical weather parameters for its development. ■

Monthly meteorological data, June to November 1979, at the Faizabad Rice Research Station, India.

Weather parameter	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov
Rainfall (mm)	27.2	182.2	31.2	21.2	39.0	22.4
Rainy days (no.)	2	12	4	2	4	1
Relative humidity (%)	63	84	81	79	85	84
Max temp (° C)	38.7	33.7	34.6	35.7	33.5	32.0
Bright sunshine (h)	9.7	6.9	9.7	9.5	9.4	8.9

Incidence and chemical control of ufra in boro fields

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A survey of ufra disease on boro rice was conducted in the Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra Project area in 1979 because ufra had appeared on transplanted aman rice in that area in 1978. Skipping 1979, the disease reappeared in 1980 and affected about 1.2 ha of transplanted IR8 severely in boro (Nov to Apr). Eighty percent of the crop of the heavily infected patches was completely lost.

To reduce disease severity and yield

loss due to ufra, carbofuran 3G was soil incorporated in the mild ufra-infected portion. Reduction in disease spread and severity was observed in the treated plots compared with the control (see table).

The yields of the treated plots and the control differed significantly. Carbofuran 3G at 34 kg/ha appeared best in controlling ufra and reducing yield loss. ■

Yield and ufra severity in carbofuran-treated and control plots of IR8, Dacca, Bangladesh, 1980:

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)	Ufra severity (%)
Control	1.43 b	5.67 b
17 kg carbofuran 3G/ha	1.69 b	4.67 ab
34 kg carbofuran 3G/ha	2.93 a	1.67 a

^a Mean of 3 replications. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different.

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effect of time of nitrogen application on weed growth and yield of dry-seeded rice

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Different amounts of nitrogen were incorporated into the soil before planting and applied as topdressing to dry-seeded wetland IR36 rice to determine the effect of time of nitrogen application on weed growth and crop yield.

Some plots received no basal applica-